

THE ROLE OF RHYMES AND SONGS IN DEVELOPING PHONOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS.

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***Abstract.** This paper explores the cultivation of using phonological competence through rhymes and songs in primary school learners. Rhymes and songs provide engaging activities that support key phonological awareness skills, such as identifying rhyming words and recognizing phonemes in interactive and enjoyable manner, also, boost motivation, engagement, and literacy development. It examines combination of qualitative observations and quantitative methods is employed to evaluate learners' progress.*

***Keywords.** Rhymes, Songs, Primary School Learners, Phonological Competence, Phonological Awareness, Phoneme Manipulation, Participation, Motivation.*

Introduction. Rhymes and songs play a vital role in cultivating phonological competence as they expose individuals to rhythmic and sounds patterns of language. Children, especially primary school learners, indeed, enjoy singing songs, dancing to the rhythm, by clapping, stomping their feet, and shaking their bodies, while dancing. Also, it creates a lively classroom atmosphere during the lesson (Isabel Maria, 2015, p.88). In addition, it facilitates the early development of literacy skills and phonological awareness. With these abilities, children are better equipped to handle reading and writing (Unal Gezer, 2021).

Description of the Case Study

This study focuses on the introduction rhymes and songs in expanding phonological competence midst primary school learners, aged 6-10. It analyzes how to refine fluency, pronunciation, intonation, confident and how teachers should keep effectively involve students in the learning process.

Analyze the Findings

The findings of this study reveal important insights into the impact of songs and rhymes on developing phonological competence in primary school learners:

Increased Motivation: Children are more inspired when authentic materials are used (rhymes, song, realia...) rather than artificial non-authentic materials (course books). It increases the children's concentration and level of involvement (Isabel Maria, 2015, p. 85).

Enhanced Fluency and Confidence: Rhymes and songs with their repetitive and rhythmic qualities can provide good prospects to work on their pronunciation, which leads to the strong confidence and range of vocabulary (Isabel Maria, 2015, p. 89).

Peer Support: When students participate together, they may encourage each other. Students who are not engaged in singing can be sustained by their classmates and maintain positive and amused atmosphere simultaneously (Şener & Erkan, 2018).

Evaluate the Methodology

This study used reliable methods, including classroom observation, interactive activities, and motivational accompanying. Combining qualitative and quantitative assessments make us realize about learners' phonological competence entirely. Qualitative data emphasize detailed, contextual understanding of each student's strengths and weaknesses, while quantitative give objective, measurable evidence of progress.

Identify the Strengths and Weaknesses of the Teaching Practices

Strengths of the Methodology:

Classroom Enjoyment: Using rhymes and songs naturally, students can be encouraged in participation and it creates fun classroom environment.

Stress Reduction: According to Unal Gezer, (2021) singing songs and using rhymes during the lesson, children are getting experience less stressful and engaging with phonological exercises more easily in this format.

Lesson Fluidity: Rhymes and songs can be used at any time in the lesson, whether at the beginning, middle, and at the end to calm down, energize or transition between activities. (Millington, 2011).

Weaknesses of the Methodology:

Participation Variability: Students who are especially modest or lack of confidence, can still feel self-conscious or confuse in taking part in singing, while others are likely enjoy their time.

Peer Dependence: Students who are not confident in matching some phonological exercises, they can rely on their peers to “cover up” their gaps skills. This situation is difficult for teacher to accurately assess students’ phonological abilities (Şener & Erkan, 2018).

Subskill Complexity: Students cannot fully assimilate all aspects of phonological competence due to the surface-level of phonological awareness. Even though, songs and rhymes are effective for engaging students, but they may not address deeper skills like phonemic awareness that refers to the phoneme manipulation (Unal Gezer, 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendation. Rhymes and songs are effective tools for amplifying phonological competence in primary school learners. By integrating rhymes and songs into classroom activities, learners have possibility to enhance their pronunciation, motivation, and fluency. By following these recommendations, teachers can maximize students’ potential in using rhymes and songs to develop phonological competence:

Material Selection: Choosing rhymes and songs that corresponded learners’ age, linguistic level, and cultural context of the learners.

Develop Clear Rubrics: Creating simple rubrics for assessment phonological skills of learners during rhyming and singing activities.

Integrate Technology: Using digital tools, such as apps or videos with rhymes and songs to embed the diversity and assess phonological competence.

Personal Reflection. By integrating Phonological awareness into early-stage of education it is the best way for developing literacy and fluency skills. Reflecting on my personal experience, incorporating rhymes and songs highly refined my students' learning results. For example, using prominent children's song to teach vowel sounds not only made the classroom environment more charmed, but also aided my students understand the concepts effectively.

REFERENCES

1. Isabel María García Conesa, Antonio Daniel Juan Rubio Universidad Castilla-La Mancha, 2015 [The use of rhymes and songs in the teaching of English in Primary Education](#)
2. Millington N.T. (2011). Using songs effectively to teach English to young learners. *Language Educational in Asia*, 2(1).
3. Şener, S. & Erkan, D. (2018). The Effect of Songs on Primary School Students' Motivation. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 5(4),867-875.
4. Unal Gezer, M. (2021). Storybooks, Songs, and Games: Tools to Boost Early Literacy Development in Primary English Classrooms. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 8(4). 2683-2700.